

ROLE OF EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY FOR GENDER EMPOWERMENT

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Abstract

Gender empowerment is to make the people of all genders socially, psychologically, physically, politically, financially and spiritually sound; without any discrimination. Conventionally and traditionally the term 'empowerment' is usually co-related to the women, though it has an impact on other marginalized genders in a distinct social or political context. To overcome obstacles such as poverty, gender-discrimination, racial-discrimination, etc. there is a need to find an appropriate solution to tackle them.

Education has always played a vital role in overcoming various problems in all spheres of life. It has helped to vent-out one's thoughts and emotions by means of healthy criticism and productive interaction. Both, at national and international front, it is seen that education has been instrumental in bridging the gap between the vulnerable and non-vulnerable groups.

Just as education, technology has also helped to change the outlook of individuals with respect to gender discrimination. With the advent of new ICTs, the internet and mobile phones in particular, have transformed the time-space discrimination. It has not only been effective in economic, social and political spheres of various societies, but also helped the marginalized groups to become more democratic and inclusive in the mainstream. Hence, it has provided a new identity and voice to the individuals irrespective of their social or economic status.

Gender Sensitization can be incorporated in classrooms by the teachers while interacting with the students. It would promote equality amongst the students and broaden their vision too.

To conclude, empowerment has many synonyms and meanings. Human empowerment dwells in identifying one's potentials, striving towards one's goals effortlessly and achieving the set goals.

Key words: *Gender Empowerment, Gender sensitization, equality, inclusive.*

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Introduction

Education has always played an immense role in the economic growth of various nations across the globe. It encompasses a blend of knowledge and technology which leads to an increase in the productivity of the nations.

Quality education helps to focus on the dimension of knowledge to merge with the apt and effective instructive framework, thus producing educated, disciplined as well as innovative thinkers. The question still remains unanswered if Education and Technology has an impact on the gender empowerment.

Need for the study

21st century is a hope of connecting education with technology. To build up a society groomed with knowledge and application, education plays a vital role at all stages- Primary, Secondary as well as Higher education. According to Haddad, Wadi D. and Jurich, Sonia (2002), ICT can increase learner motivation and engagement, by facilitating acquisition of basic skills.

National Education Policy-2020 aims a goal of transforming to meet the needs of 21st century India. It focusses to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through school and higher education institutions across India.

Modern technologies have modified how individuals socialize within the inter and intra communities. This leads to a number of issues which need to be addressed by educators and policy makers too. Thus, this paper tries to highlight the impact of Education and Technology on the gender, which subsequently could lead to the progress of the society at large.

Based on the review of related literature it is seen that some studies reported a positive relation between Education and Technology on Gender empowerment. At the same time there are studies that show negative relation between Education and Technology on Gender empowerment. Due to this gap, the researcher felt the need to conduct this study to compare the relationship between Education and Technology on Gender empowerment.

Statement of the problem:

Role of Education and Technology on Gender Empowerment

Definition of important terms:

- i. **Education-** Education implies to gain basic knowledge of reading, writing and arithmetic.
- ii. **Technology-** Technology is a tool to develop objectives-knowledge, understanding, application and skill; besides enhancing communication.
- iii. **Gender-** Gender refers to the socially constructed characteristics- norms, roles and relationships of and between men and women.
- iv. **Empowerment-** Empowerment implies the degree of autonomy and self-determination in people of different communities.

Aim of the study:

To study the effectiveness of Education and Technology on Gender Empowerment.

Research questions

Is there a relation between role of education and gender empowerment?

Is there a significant correlation between technology and gender empowerment?

Objectives of the study

To study the effectiveness of Education and Technology on Gender empowerment on the basis of geographical location, amenities provided as well as time spent.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of effectiveness of Education and Technology on gender empowerment on the basis of- i) geographical location ii) amenities provided and iii) time spent.

Method of the study

Survey method was used to collect the required data. The researcher administered a questionnaire for the same.

Analysis of data

The raw data was tabulated and the mean scores of the effectiveness of Education and Technology on Gender empowerment on the basis of geographical location, amenities provided as well as time spent was found out. These scores were compared using one way ANOVA.

Mean scores of effectiveness of Education and Technology on gender empowerment on the basis of geographical location	47.5216481
Mean scores of effectiveness of Education and Technology on gender empowerment on the basis of amenities provided	47.0234837
Mean scores of effectiveness of Education and Technology on gender empowerment on the basis of time spent	39.6557908

Table 2 F value table

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F
Between groups	3164.624	2	1582.312	11.053
Within groups	32354.069	226	143.159	
Total	35518.693	228		

Results and Discussions:

The obtained F value is more than the critical value at all levels of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stands rejected and therefore it can be concluded that there is significant difference in the mean scores on the effectiveness of Education and Technology on Gender empowerment on the basis of geographical location, amenities provided as well as time spent.

Based on the above-mentioned results, it can be put forth that there is a sincere need of Education and Technology in gender empowerment. Thus, it is suggested that an awareness should be created amongst the people of various strata of the society. Essential measure should be implemented, monitored and evaluated at regular intervals to assess its feasibility too.

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